

PREDICTING THE DEFORMATIVE AND THERMAL CHARACTERISTICS OF HYBRID COMPOSITES

V. A. Kochetkov and R.D. Maksimov
(Institute of Polymer Mechanics, Latvian SSR
Academy of Sciences, Riga, USSR)

ABSTRACT

A theoretical and experimental investigation was carried out to examine the possibilities of a structural approach for prediction of elastic constants, creep functions and thermal characteristics of hybrid polymer composites reinforced with anisotropic fibres of several types. The problem of determining effective characteristics of the composite was solved by generalizing the self-consistent method for the case of a three phase model. Exact analytical expressions were obtained for elastic constants, thermal expansion coefficients, conductivity coefficients and specific heat of a unidirectional hybrid composite. The effect of brittle fibres breakdown under tension in the direction of reinforcement of a unidirectional hybrid composite was studied in the conditions of a short-term loading and long-term creep. Unlike to the well-known notion about a "slowed fracture" at creep of two-component composites, it is shown that in hybrid composites it is the creep of viscoelastic fibres in axial direction that contributes most to the brittle fibres breakdown. The peculiarities of thermal expansion of hybrid composites and the possibilities for the purposeful control of thermal expansion coefficients by hybridization were studied. The considered thermal interval included a region of transition of the polymer matrix from a glass state into a viscoelastic one. The experimental confirmation of the prediction results was done on specimens of organic-glass, organic-carbon, glass-carbon and organic-boron polymer composites with different ratios of volume contents of fibres.

INTRODUCTION

The industry manufactures now a wide range of reinforced fibres. Yet using only two-component (monofibrous) composites, it is difficult to meet the requirements applied by practice to rigidity and short-, long-term or fatigue strength, impact resistance, cost and weight, damping properties, thermal and other characteristics of composites. Therefore, it is natural that there is interest in hybridization, i.e. in combination of more than one type of fibres in a common matrix. A hybrid effect in strength has been studied in¹⁻⁶ and other works. A statistical approach to description of the process of fibres breakdown in a hybrid composite under a short-term loading has been given in⁷⁻⁹. The problem of hybridization has been considered also in¹⁰⁻¹³. This paper examines the possibilities of a unitary structural approach for prediction of a complex of deformative (including long-term) and thermophysical properties of hybrids.

CHARACTERISTICS OF ELASTIC AND THERMAL PROPERTIES

Effective characteristics of the elastic and thermophysical properties are determined for the case of a unidirectional hybrid composite reinforced with transversely-isotropic fibres of N types, which are distributed randomly with respect to one another.

I. The calculation model for determining the stress and strain fields in the components of the hybrid composite is shown in Fig. I. Here F1 and F2 are the fibres of types I and 2; M is the matrix phase; EHM is the equivalent homogeneous medium, whose elastic constants coincide with effective elastic constants of the hybrid composite. The stress and strain fields in components were determined from the solution of the system of equations of equilibrium in displacements for specified values applied to composite stresses σ_{ij} with use of a three phase model (Fig. I). The stresses and strains were determined at first for the fibre of type I and surrounding layer of the matrix, after that - for the fibre of type 2, etc. The effective elastic constants of the hybrid composite were determined after averaging the stresses and strains in the components. The plane strain bulk modulus K_{I2} and the modulus of transverse shear G_{I2} were obtained¹⁴ in the forms :

$$\frac{I}{K_{I2} + G_{I2}} = \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{\mu_n}{\mu} \frac{I}{K_{I2}^{*n} + G_{I2}} \quad , \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{I}{G_{I2}} = \frac{K_{I2} + G_{I2}}{G_{I2} - G_{I2}^m} \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{\mu_n}{\mu} \frac{G_{I2}^{*n} - G_{I2}^m}{G_{I2}^{*n} (K_{I2} + G_{I2}) + \gamma K_{I2} (G_{I2} - G_{I2}^{*n})} \quad , \quad (2)$$

where N is the number of types of fibres, μ_n is the volume content of fibres of the n-th type, $\mu = \sum \mu_n$ is the total reinforcement content, G_{I2}^m is the shear modulus of the matrix,

$$K_{I2}^{*n} = \mu K_{I2}^n + (I - \mu) K_{I2}^m - (K_{I2}^n - K_{I2}^m)^2 D_I \quad ,$$

$$D_I = \mu(I - \mu) / [(I - \mu) K_{I2}^n + \mu K_{I2}^m + G_{I2}^m] \quad ,$$

$$G_{I2}^{*n} = G_{I2}^m / \left\{ I - \frac{C_{IIII}^m}{ab - c} \left[\mu \frac{c}{a} - I + \sqrt{(\mu \frac{c}{a} + I)^2 - 4\mu b} \right] \right\} \quad ,$$

$$a = K_{I2}^m (I - \mu) - 2C_{IIII}^m G_{I2}^n / (G_{I2}^n - G_{I2}^m) \quad ,$$

$$b = 3\mu(I - \mu)^2 (K_{I2}^m)^2 / a^2 \quad ,$$

$$c = (I - \mu^3) K_{I2}^m + 2\mu^3 C_{IIII}^m / (I + G_{I2}^m / G_{I2}^n + 2G_{I2}^m / K_{I2}^n) \quad ,$$

$$\gamma = 0.5 - I.5 \frac{x(I - \mu)^2 (K_{I2}^m)^2 (I + G_{I2}^m / G_{I2}^n + 2G_{I2}^m / K_{I2}^n)}{(2C_{IIII}^m - xc)(2C_{IIII}^m - yc)} \quad ,$$

$$x = I - G_{I2}^m / G_{I2}^{*n} , \quad y = I - G_{I2}^m / G_{I2} , \quad C_{IIII}^m = K_{I2}^m + G_{I2}^m .$$

Here subscript n denotes the elastic constants of fibres of the n-th type, subscript m corresponds to the matrix. The longitudinal modulus E_3 , Poisson's ratio ν_{I3} and shear modulus G_{I3} were obtained^{I4} in the forms :

$$E_3 = \sum_{n=I}^N \frac{\mu_n}{\mu} [E_3^{*n} - 4\nu_{I3}^{*n} (\nu_{I3} - \nu_{I3}^{*n}) G_{I2} K_{I2}^{*n} / (G_{I2} + K_{I2}^{*n})] , \quad (3)$$

$$\nu_{I3} = (I + G_{I2} / K_{I2}) \sum_{n=I}^N \frac{\mu_n}{\mu} \nu_{I3}^{*n} K_{I2}^{*n} / (G_{I2} + K_{I2}^{*n}) , \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{I}{G_{I3}} = \sum_{n=I}^N \frac{\mu_n}{\mu} \frac{2}{G_{I3} + G_{I3}^{*n}} , \quad (5)$$

where

$$E_3^{*n} = \mu E_3^n + (I - \mu) E_3^m + 4(\nu_{I3}^n - \nu_{I3}^m)^2 D_2 ,$$

$$\nu_{I3}^{*n} = \mu \nu_{I3}^n + (I - \mu) \nu_{I3}^m + (\nu_{I3}^n - \nu_{I3}^m) (I / K_{I2}^m - I / K_{I2}^n) D_2 ,$$

$$D_2 = \mu (I - \mu) / [(I - \mu) / K_{I2}^n + \mu / K_{I2}^m + I / G_{I2}^m] ,$$

$$G_{I3}^{*n} = G_{I3}^m [G_{I3}^n (I + \mu) + G_{I3}^m (I - \mu)] / [G_{I3}^n (I - \mu) + G_{I3}^m (I + \mu)] .$$

If we put $N=I$ in (I)-(5), than we will easy establish the meaning of the quantities K_{I2}^{*n} , G_{I2}^{*n} , E_3^{*n} , ν_{I3}^{*n} and G_{I3}^{*n} . These quantities are effective elastic constants of a composite reinforced with fibres of one (n-th) type.

2. For determining the effective coefficients of thermal expansion, an equilibrium state of an unloaded composite after its heating from temperature T_0 to $T_0 + \Delta T$ was considered^{I5}. The stress and strain fields in components were determined analogously to the previous problem. For transverse α_I and longitudinal α_3 coefficients of thermal expansion were obtained the following expressions :

$$\alpha_I = -\nu_{I3} \alpha_3 + (I + G_{I2} / K_{I2}) \sum_{n=I}^N \frac{\mu_n}{\mu} \frac{K_{I2}^{*n}}{G_{I2} + K_{I2}^{*n}} \frac{\alpha_I^{*n} + \nu_{I3}^{*n} \alpha_3^{*n}}{G_{I2} + K_{I2}^{*n}} ,$$

$$\alpha_3 = \frac{I}{E_3} \sum_{n=I}^N \frac{\mu_n}{\mu} \left[\alpha_3^{*n} E_3^{*n} + 4(\nu_{I3}^{*n} - \nu_{I3}) G_{I2} K_{I2}^{*n} \frac{\alpha_I^{*n} + \nu_{I3}^{*n} \alpha_3^{*n}}{G_{I2} + K_{I2}^{*n}} \right] ,$$

where α_I^{*n} , α_3^{*n} are thermal expansion coefficients of a composite reinforced with fibres of one (n-th) type :

$$\alpha_I^{*n} = -\nu_{I3}^{*n} \alpha_3^{*n} + \mu (\alpha_I^n + \nu_{I3}^n \alpha_3^n) + (1-\mu) (\alpha_I^m + \nu_{I3}^m \alpha_3^m) + \\ + (\alpha_I^n + \nu_{I3}^n \alpha_3^n - \alpha_I^m - \nu_{I3}^m \alpha_3^m) (1/K_{I2}^m - 1/K_{I2}^n) D_2 ,$$

$$\alpha_3^{*n} = \left[\mu \alpha_3^n E_3^n + (1-\mu) \alpha_3^m E_3^m + \right. \\ \left. + (\nu_{I3}^n - \nu_{I3}^m) (\alpha_I^n + \nu_{I3}^n \alpha_3^n - \alpha_I^m - \nu_{I3}^m \alpha_3^m) D_2 \right] / E_3^{*n} .$$

It should be noted that the present approach allows to calculate not only the elastic constants and thermal expansion coefficients of the hybrid composite, but also the stresses, including the thermal ones, in components^{I6}.

3. For determining the heat capacity of the hybrid composite, the change in the internal energy of a unit volume of the composite with its slow heating from temperature T_0 to $T_0 + dT$ was examined. The temperature field in composite at each moment of time was assumed to be uniform. The first law of thermodynamics was used. As a result the following expression for the heat capacity at constant deformation c_ε was obtained^{I5}, which considered the energy spent on the work against the elastic forces arising in components during their thermal expansion :

$$\rho c_\varepsilon = \sum_{n=I}^N \frac{\mu_n}{\mu} \left\{ \rho^{*n} c_\varepsilon^{*n} + T_0 \left[\frac{(\beta_I^{*n})^2}{G_{I2} + K_{I2}^{*n}} - \frac{(\beta_I)^2}{G_{I2} + K_{I2}} \right] \right\} ,$$

where

$$\rho^{*n} c_\varepsilon^{*n} = \mu \rho_n c_\varepsilon^n + (1-\mu) \rho_m c_\varepsilon^m + T_0 (\beta_I^n - \beta_I^m)^2 D_I , \quad \rho = \sum_{n=I}^N \frac{\mu_n}{\mu} \rho^{*n} , \\ \rho^{*n} = \mu \rho_n + (1-\mu) \rho_m , \quad \beta_I = 2K_{I2} (\alpha_I + \nu_{I3} \alpha_3) .$$

4. For determining the temperature distribution and the heat fluxes in components in the case of stationary temperature field, a heat conduction equation was solved. As in the previous problems, a three phase model was used. After averaging the temperature gradients and heat fluxes in components the transverse λ_I and longitudinal λ_3 effective conductivity coefficients of the hybrid composite were obtained^{I5} in the form :

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_I} = \sum_{n=I}^N \frac{\mu_n}{\mu} \frac{2}{\lambda_I + \lambda_I^{*n}} , \quad \lambda_3 = \sum_{n=I}^N \frac{\mu_n}{\mu} \lambda_3^{*n} ,$$

where λ_I^{*n} , λ_3^{*n} are the conductivity coefficients of a composite reinforced with fibres of one (n-th) type :

$$\lambda_I^{*n} = \lambda_I^m [\lambda_I^n (1+\mu) + \lambda_I^m (1-\mu)] / [\lambda_I^n (1-\mu) + \lambda_I^m (1+\mu)] , \\ \lambda_3^{*n} = \lambda_3^n \mu + \lambda_3^m (1-\mu)$$

5. The calculated and experimental data were compared for four types

of hybrids with epoxy matrix EDT-10 : organic-glass, organic-carbon, glass-carbon and organic-boron composites with different ratios of volume contents of fibres of two types. As an example, the calculated and experimental elastic constants and thermal expansion coefficients of aⁿ unidirectional organic-carbon composite in relation to the volume content of organic (μ_0) and carbon (μ_c) fibres are shown in Fig. 2. Calculations were made with the same elastic constants of components, as in^{I4}, and with the following thermal expansion coefficients : for the epoxy matrix $\alpha_m = 70 \cdot 10^{-6} K^{-1}$ (experimental value); for the organic fibres $\alpha_I^o = 65.6 \cdot 10^{-6} K^{-1}$, $\alpha_2^o = -7.2 \cdot 10^{-6} K^{-1}$; for the carbon fibres $\alpha_I^c = 33.3 \cdot 10^{-6} K^{-1}$, $\alpha_3^c = -0.56 \cdot 10^{-6} K^{-1}$ (α_I and α_3 of fibres were calculated from experimental data for organic/epoxy and carbon/epoxy composites on temperature interval [20°C, 40°C]).

INFLUENCE OF FIBRES FRACTURE ON SHORT-TERM DEFORMATION AND CREEP OF HYBRID COMPOSITE

It is known that in hybrid composites reinforced with brittle (having small ultimate strains) and high-elongation fibres, the process of brittle fibres fracture may start long before a macroscopic rupture of the composite as a whole. The method of prediction of a short-term deformation and a long-term creep of aⁿ hybrid composite with allowance for the effect of brittle fibres fracture and the related process of stress redistribution between the components was proposed in^{I7-20}. We assumed that the hybrid composite consisted of elastic high-modulus brittle fibres and aⁿ homogeneous transversely-isotropic matrix, which substituted the binder reinforced with less-modulus viscoelastic fibres. By using the solution^{I7} for the problem of redistribution of stresses in the environment of the fibre fracture (the calculation model is shown in Fig. 3) and characterizing the strength of the brittle fibres by a Weibull distribution, in^{I8, I9} the following expression for the longitudinal modulus E_3 in relation to the strain $\epsilon_{33} > 0$ with allowance for the effect of fibre fracture was obtained :

$$E_3(\epsilon_{33}) = \mu E_3^f \left[1 - \frac{\sigma^i}{l_0 N_0} \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \text{th}(l_0/\sigma^i/2^i) \cdot \sum_{j=0}^i b_{ij} e^{-c_j \epsilon_{33}^{\beta}} \right] + (1-\mu) E_3^m, \quad (6)$$

where

$$\sigma^i = r_f \sqrt{(E_3^m - E_3^f) \ln \mu + E_3^m (1/\mu - 1)} / \sqrt{G_{I3}^m}; \quad b_{00} = N_0;$$

$$b_{ii} = - \sum_{k=0}^{i-1} b_{ik}, \quad i \geq 1; \quad b_{ij} = 2b_{i-1,j} c_{i-1} / (c_i - c_j), \quad i > j;$$

$$c_i = \alpha l_0 (E_3^f)^{\beta} [1 - I / \text{ch}(l_0/\sigma^i/2^i)]^{\beta} / 2^i.$$

Here μ is the volume content of (brittle) fibres, α and β are the parameters of a Weibull's distribution of fibres strength, σ^i is ineffective length of brittle fibres, N_0 is the number of fibres of length l_0 .

In order to obtain (6) it was assumed that fibres of length l_i fractured under action of the maximal (along the length of a fibre)

stress and, as a result, two segments of equal length $l_{i+I} = l_i/2$ formed. The averaged experimental $\sigma_e(\epsilon_{33})$ and calculated $\sigma_{33} = \epsilon_{33} E_3(\epsilon_{33})$ deformation diagrams of an organic-boron composite with volume content of boron fibres $\mu_b = 0.09$ and organic fibres $\mu_o = 0.31$ for loading at a rate $\dot{\sigma}_{33} = 50$ MPa/min are compared in Fig. 4. The limited divergence between these diagrams at $\sigma_{33} > 500$ MPa may be a consequence of the debonding of boron fibres from epoxy matrix at their fracture. The calculated curve for the change in the defectiveness of the composite $P = 1 - E_3(\epsilon_{33})/E_3(0)$ corresponded well to the experimentally revealed nonmonotonic change in the intensity of acoustic emission (AE) during the elongation of the unidirectional hybrid composite. The process of fracture of the brittle fibres at a creep of hybrid composite was modelled on a computer with the algorithm of the program given in²⁰. At first, the increments in stresses in the brittle fibres due to manifestation of the viscoelasticity of the matrix and non-brittle fibres were calculated. After that by using a Weibull's distribution of the strength of brittle fibres, the number of fractured fibres was determined. After that the increments in stresses of components due to unloading of brittle fibres in the environment of the fracture were calculated. From the calculated increments in stresses, an additional number of fractured fibres was determined, and so on. For a new value of a time, the increments in stresses in the brittle fibres arising due to manifestation of the viscoelasticity of the matrix and non-brittle fibres were calculated, and so on. The calculation results (curves) and experimental data (points) for a creep of an organic-boron composite with the organic fibres content $\mu_o = 0.31$ and the boron fibres content $\mu_b = 0.09$ under stress $\sigma_{33} = 750$ MPa are compared in Fig. 5. Curve I was computed with the algorithm described above, curve 3 was computed disregarding the fibres fracture. Curve 2 was computed with allowance for fibres fracture and the viscoelastic properties of the homogeneous matrix at shear in the vicinity of fibre rupture, while the law of elastic matrix deformation was adopted in the direction of elongation of the composite. These conditions were analogous to those of the "slow-rupture" model²¹, with a difference that the elastic tensile modulus of the matrix representing here the binder reinforced with non-brittle viscoelastic fibres, was taken into account. Comparing curves I-3 with the experimental data we may conclude that a creep of viscoelastic fibres in the direction of reinforcement plays a principal role in a hybrid composite. It is just this creep that significantly increases the fibre damage during creep of the composite.

THERMAL DEFORMATION

Let us assume that thermoviscoelastic deformation of the matrix and viscoelastic fibres may be described with linear integral equations of a hereditary type :

$$\epsilon_{ij}^n(t) = \int_0^t I_{ijkl}^n(t-t', T) \frac{d\sigma_{kl}^n(t')}{dt'} dt' + \int_{T_0}^T \alpha_{ij}^n(T) dT, \quad (7)$$

where $n=0$ corresponds to the matrix and $n=1, 2, \dots$ corresponds to the fibres. We assume also that for functions $I_{ijkl}^n(t, T)$ are executed

the temperature-time analogy. This means that the values $I_{ijkl}^n(t, T)$ at $T = \text{const}$ may be obtained from the values $I_{ijkl}^n(t, T_r)$, where $T_r = \text{const}$, by changing the scale of time :

$$I_{ijkl}^n(t, T) = I_{ijkl}^n(a_T t, T_r) .$$

The dependence of the temperature-time reduction coefficient a_T on the temperature is taken according to the Williams-Landel-Ferry equation :

$$\ln a_T = c_1(T - T_r) / [1 + c_2(T - T_r)] ,$$

where T_r is the reduction temperature. It might be noted that a_T for different components of tensor I_{ijkl}^n (i.e. for different sets of subscripts $ijkl$) should not obligatory coincide with one another. With the temperature changing in time, $I_{ijkl}^n(t, T)$ may be computed in the scale of modified time :

$$I_{ijkl}^n(t, T) = I_{ijkl}^n(t_m, T_r) = J_{ijkl}^n(t) , \quad (8)$$

where

$$t_m = \int_0^{T(t)} a_T [T(t')] dt' ,$$

and, in general case, t_m is different for different components of tensor I_{ijkl}^n (i.e. for different values of $ijkl$). By using (8), eq.(7) takes the following form :

$$\epsilon_{ij}^n(t) = \int_0^t J_{ijkl}^n(t-t') \frac{d\sigma_{kl}^n}{dt'} dt' + \int_{T_0}^{T(t)} \alpha_{ij}^n(T) dT . \quad (9)$$

If we apply the Laplace transformation to (9), we will find the following equations, which are analogous to the equations of a thermoelastic problem :

$$\bar{\epsilon}_{ij}^n(p) = p J_{ijkl}^n(p) \bar{\sigma}_{kl}^n(p) + \bar{\epsilon}_{ij}^{nT}(p) ,$$

where the upper line is used to designate the complex functions-representations of the Laplace transformation, p is the transformation parameter and

$$\bar{\epsilon}_{ij}^{nT}(p) = \int_0^\infty e^{-pt} \int_{T_0}^{T(t)} \alpha_{ij}^n(T) dT dt .$$

By using the solution^{I4, I5} of a thermo-elastic problem where compliances I_{ijkl}^n of the components are replaced by $p J_{ijkl}^n(p)$, the expressions $\alpha_{ij}^n \Delta T$ are replaced by $\bar{\epsilon}_{ij}^{nT}(p)$, the stresses and strains in components are replaced by its representations in a space of the Laplace transformation, we shall obtain the function-representation for the searched solution - for the strains of the thermal expansion of a unidirectional hybrid composite. After the inversion of the Laplace transformation we will determine the tensor of strains of the thermal expansion $\epsilon_{ij}^n(t)$ of a hybrid composite as a function of a time for gi-

ven law of changing of the temperature with time $T(t)$. The experimental and computed by the described approach values of transverse ϵ_{II} and longitudinal ϵ_{33} strains of thermal expansion of an organic-glass hybrid with different contents of the organic and glass fibres at heating with a rate $dT/dt=50^{\circ}C/h$ are compared in Fig. 6. It is seen that by varying the contents of the two types of fibres the thermal expansion strain in the direction of reinforcement may be significantly changed, and this changing may be predicted with acceptable accuracy.

REFERENCES

1. Hayashi T. et al., Fukugo Zairyo, I(1972), 2I.
2. Hayashi T., In: Proc. 8th Int. Reinf. Plas. Conf., Brighton, UK, (1972), I49.
3. Bunsell A.R. and Harris B., Composites, 5(1974), I57.
4. Aveston J. and Sillwood J.M., J.Mat.Sci., II(1976), I877.
5. Zweben C., J.Mat.Sci., I2(1977), I325.
6. Bader M.G. and Priest A.M., In: Proc. ICCM-IV, Tokyo, (1982), II29.
7. Fukuda H. and Chou T.W., In: Proc. ICCM-IV, Tokyo, (1982), II45.
8. Fukuda H., J.Mat.Sci., I9(1984), 974.
9. Gutans J. and Tamuzs V., Theor.Appl.Fract.Mech., 7(1987), I93.
10. Skudra A.M. et al., Pol.Mech.(transl. from Russian), (1974), 57.
11. Gunyaev G.M., Pol.Mech., (1978), 685.
12. Laws N., Int.J.Eng.Sci., I2(1974), 79.
13. Laws N. and McLaughlin R., J.Mech.Phys.Solids, 27(1979), I.
14. Kochetkov V.A., Mech.Comp.Mater.(transl. from Russian), (1987), 33.
15. Kochetkov V.A., Mech.Comp.Mater., (1987), I78.
16. Kochetkov V.A., Algorithms and Programs (in Russian), (1988), No. 4, 4.
17. Kochetkov V.A. and Maksimov R.D., Mech.Comp.Mater., (1981), 672.
18. Maksimov R.D. and Kochetkov V.A., Mech.Comp.Mater., (1982), I57.
19. Maksimov R.D., Kochetkov V.A. and Ponomarjev V.M., In: Methods and Means of Composite Structures (in Russian), Riga, Zinatne, (1983), I37.
20. Kochetkov V.A. and Maksimov R.D., Mech.Comp.Mater., (1984), 668.
21. Lifshits S.T., In: Composite Materials (Russian transl.), V.5, Moscow, (1978), 267.
22. Urzhumcev J.S. and Maksimov R.D. Prognostics of Deformativity of Polymer Composites (in Russian), Riga, Zinatne, (1975).

Fig. I. The calculation model

Fig. 2 The calculated (lines) and experimental (points) elastic constants and thermal expansion coefficients of an organic-carbon hybrid composite vs volume content of organic (μ_0) and carbon (μ_c) fibres.

Fig. 3 The calculation model with allowance for the brittle fibres fracture.

Fig. 4 Predicted ($\sigma \sim \epsilon$) and experimental ($\sigma_e \sim \epsilon$) stress-strain curves of an organic-boron hybrid composite and characteristics of damage process.

Fig. 5 A long-term creep of an organic-boron hybrid composite and its prediction results.

Fig. 6 Transverse (a) and longitudinal (b) strains of thermal expansion of an organic-glass hybrid composite with different ratios of volume contents of the organic (μ_0) and glass (μ_g) fibres: 1 - $\mu_0=0.50$, $\mu_g=0$; 2 - 0.40, 0.10; 3 - 0.29, 0.21; 4 - 0.18, 0.32; 5 - 0, 0.50. Points - experimental values, lines - prediction results.